

**“ULTRASOUND STUDY OF
GALL BLADDER DISEASES”**

By

Dr.HOLEBASU

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Under the guidance of

Dr.B.R.DHAMANGAONKAR_{M.D}

PROFESSOR

DEPARTMENT OF RADIO-DIAGNOSIS

B.L.D.E.U'S SHRI B. M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE

HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYPUR

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Date:

Place: Vijaypur

Dr.HOLEBASU
Post Graduate Student,
Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical
College, Hospital & Research Centre,
Vijaypur.

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Date:

Place: Vijaypur **Dr.B.R.DHAMANGAONKAR** **M.D.**

Professor
Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre, Vijaypur.

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**SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
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This to certify that the dissertation entitled "**ULTRASOUND STUDY OF GALL BLADDER DISEASES**" is a bonafideresearch work done by **Dr.HOLEBASU** under the guidance of **Dr.B.R.DHAMANGAONKAR** Professor Department of Radiodiagnosis at B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijaypur.

Date:

Place: Vijaypur

Dr. BHUSHAN N. LAKHKAR_{M.D.}
Professor and HOD

Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U's
Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre, Vijaypur.

**B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY'S
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL &
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Date:

Place: Vijaypur.

Dr. S. P. GUGGARIGUDAR

Principal, B.L.D.E.U's
Shri B. M. Patil Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre,
Vijaypur.

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Date:

Place: Vijaypur

Dr.HOLEBASU

Post Graduate Student,
Department of Radiodiagnosis,
B.L.D.E.U's Shri B. M. Patil Medical
College, Hospital & Research Centre,
Vijaypur.

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Date:

Place: Vijayapur.

Dr. Holebasu

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND & OBJECTIVES

Diseases of the gall bladder include wide spectrum of pathologies. Conditions like cholelithiasis, acute cholecystitis, membranous cholecystitis, present with right upper quadrant pain other conditions like gall bladder polyp are asymptomatic. In many cases of carcinoma gall bladder the symptoms manifests very late, when conservative and curative treatment is not possible. In such conditions the inclusion of ultrasound abdomen in routine investigation protocol will help in early diagnosis and initiation of therapy.

SOURCE OF DATA:

The source of data for this study is patients referred to the DEPARTMENT OF RADIOLOGY AND IMAGING at Shri B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research center, Bijapur for transabdominal ultrasound.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To describe sonographic findings in spectrum of gall bladder diseases.
- To discuss the advantages and limitations of ultrasound in diagnosis and differentiation of gall bladder diseases.
- To correlate clinical diagnosis with ultrasound diagnosis.
- Comparison with CT/MRI where ever possible.

METHODS AND MATERIAL

Patients with gall bladder diseases usually presents with pain in the right hypochondriac region which may be radiating to the epigastrium or around the lower ribs or to the back. Evaluation of the gallbladder by ultrasound was performed in sagittal and transverse planes with low frequency and high frequency sector probes. To avoid missing gall bladder pathologies special maneuver such as subcostal oblique view with the left edge of the transducer more cephalad than the right edge is used. An attempt to elicit sonological Murphy's sign will be made in order to detect cholecystitis.

RESULTS

- In a series of 202 cases, majority of the gall bladder diseases includes gall stones. Among non calculus diseases inflammatory conditions, acute cholecystitis was commonest, others include chronic cholecystitis, membranous cholecystitis, polyp, perforation, adenomyomatosis.
- In our study neoplasms were rare compared to inflammatory conditions of which malignant were more common than benign.

CONCLUSION

The ultrasound diagnosis in gall bladder diseases had favourable & impressive results against clinical diagnosis.

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INTRODUCTION

Diseases of the gallbladder include wide spectrum ranging from gallstones, sludge, polyps, gallbladder mucocele, porcelain gallbladder, inflammatory conditions and neoplasms, both benign and malignant.

These conditions are seen almost everyday in radiology practice, early identification of which helps in bringing down the morbidity and mortality associated with them.

The radiological evaluation of gallbladder diseases has undergone an ocean of change with the advent of ultrasound in 1978.

Oral cholecystography which was gold standard in yesteryears is no more an option due to better appreciation of gallbladder diseases by ultrasound.

Ultrasound techniques on the other hand have found greater acceptance by every faculty overwhelmingly throughout the world with its high degree of sensitivity and specificity for nearly entire spectrum of gallbladder diseases.

Several studies using ultrasound have led to the revisions in clinical approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of gallbladder diseases and hence this study of gallbladder diseases by sonography appears appropriate.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Gallbladder pathologies constitute about 8-9 cases per week referred for ultrasound to our department.

Patients with gallbladder diseases usually presents with pain in the right hypochondriac region which may be radiating to the epigastrium or around the lower ribs or to the back.

Certain conditions like carcinoma gallbladder present with vague manifestations like weight loss and other conditions like gallbladder polyp are asymptomatic.

It has also been noted that in many cases of carcinoma gallbladder, the symptoms manifests very late, when conservative and curative treatment is not possible.

It is in such conditions that the inclusion of ultrasound abdomen in routine investigation protocol will help in early diagnosis and initiation of therapy¹.

Ultrasound is easily available, reliable, has no harmful ionizing radiations and less expensive than other modalities.

Ultrasound has the highest sensitivity and specificity for evaluating patients with suspected biliary pathologies². The most important advantage of ultrasound over other imaging techniques in the investigation of acute cholecystitis is the ability to assess sonographic Murphy's sign, which is a reliable indicator of acute cholecystitis with a sensitivity of 92%³. An increased gallbladder wall thickness of > 3.5 mm has been found to be a reliable and independent predictor of acute cholecystitis⁴.

Transabdominal ultrasound is frequently the first imaging technique employed for patients presenting with biliary-type symptoms as it is more accurate than CT for diagnosing acute biliary disease⁵. Imaging is usually performed following a 4-hour fast, allowing the gallbladder to fill and reducing obscuring upper abdominal gas. Ultrasound allows dynamic assessment and by moving the patient helps differentiate stones, sludge and polyps.

Doppler ultrasound allows assessment of vascularity, while focal gallbladder tenderness can be determined using probe pressure.

Hence this study is undertaken to evaluate gallbladder pathologies by ultrasonography in diagnosis of clinically suspected cases with regard to diagnostic performance characteristics, technical success, safety and cost effectiveness.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the dissertation titled “ULTRASOUND STUDY OF GALLBLADDER DISEASES” is as follows

1. To describe sonographic findings in spectrum of gallbladder diseases.
2. To discuss the advantages and limitations of ultrasound in diagnosis and differentiation of gallbladder diseases.
3. To correlate clinical diagnosis with ultrasound diagnosis.
4. Comparison with CT/MRI where ever possible.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Source of data:

The source of data for this study is patients referred to the DEPARTMENT OF RADIOLOGY AND IMAGING at Shri B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research center, Bijapur for transabdominal ultrasound with right upper quadrant pain.

Period of Study: November 2015 - April 2017

Study Design: Cross-sectional study

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients presenting with history of abdominal pain, tenderness in right upper quadrant, clinical features of obstructive jaundice.
- Clinically diagnosed / suspected gallbladder diseases.
- Patients with previous history of gallstones.
- Known case of pancreatitis.

Exclusion criteria:

- Abdominal pain other than in right upper quadrant.
- All cases of acute abdomen like those due to peptic ulcer, hollow viscus perforation, intestinal obstruction.
- All post-operative patients of cholecystectomy.

METHODS OF COLLECTION OF DATA

All clinically suspected patients of gallbladder disease referred to the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Center for transabdominal ultrasound were included in the study.

Evaluation of the gallbladder will be performed in sagittal and transverse planes. Scanning will be performed with two probes one with low frequency (8 to 5 MHz) and one with high frequency (12 to 3 MHz).

To avoid missing gallbladder pathologies special maneuver viz, use of subcostal oblique view with the left edge of the transducer more cephalad than the right edge.

An attempt to elicit sonological Murphy's sign (maximal abdominal tenderness from pressure of the ultrasound probe over the visualized gallbladder) will be made, in order to detect cholecystitis.

Ingestion of food, particularly fatty food, stimulates the gallbladder to contract. The contracted gallbladder appears thick walled and may obscure luminal or wall abnormalities. Therefore the examination of the gallbladder should be performed after a minimum of 4 hours of fasting.

The machines which will be used in the study are SIEMENS ACUSON X700 and PHILIPS HD11-XE.

SAMPLE SIZE

Based on the incidence of patients for gallbladder diseases (0.83%)⁶, at 99% confidence level and +/-2 margin of error, the sample size calculated is 202.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 r X p X (100 - p)}{d^2}$$

Here, Z = Z is value at level

p = incidence rate

d = margin of error

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Data will be analyzed using,

Diagrams

Mean ± SD

chi square test/fisher exact test

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

EMBRYOLOGY

The gallbladder derives as an outpouching from embryonic biliary tree.

The proximal part of the pouch gives rise to cystic duct, and the distal portion forms the gallbladder.

Within the cystic duct, small mucosal folds called the spiral valves of Heister; these are identified on sonography.

FIG 1

During its initial development, the gallbladder lies in an intrahepatic position, but as it migrates to the surface of the liver, it acquires a peritoneal covering (part of liver capsule) over 50% to 70% of its surface. The remainder of the gallbladder surface is covered with adventitial tissue that merges with connective tissue in contiguity with the liver ⁶

ANATOMY

Gallbladder is a pear-shaped organ lying in the inferior border of the liver, between right and left lobes. Middle hepatic vein, interlobar fissure lies in the same

anatomic plane separating the two hepatic lobes, extends from the right portal vein origin to the gallbladder fossa and may be used to find it.

This fissure has been seen in up to 70% of hepatic ultrasound studies⁷ and used as a landmark for the gallbladder fossa.

The gallbladder is divided into three parts, the fundus, body, and neck; the fundus lies anterior and inferior segment. At the region of the gallbladder neck, there may be an infundibulum, called Hartmann's pouch, which is site for impaction of gallstones.

FIG 2

FIG 3

Primary blood supply to gallbladder is by the cystic artery, which is a branch of the right hepatic artery, and the cystic veins, which drain into the portal vein.

The gallbladder function as reservoir for the storage and concentration of bile, which is secreted by the liver, composed mainly of bile salts, bile pigments and small amounts of cholesterol, lecithin, fatty acid and mucin.

The gallbladder can store upto 50 ml of bile and can increase the concentration of bile by five to ten times.

Release of bile from the gallbladder is stimulated by the presence of fatty food, in the alimentary tract. Duodenum secretes cholecystokinin, which stimulates contraction of the gallbladder and reflexive contractions of wall of gallbladder both in conjunction with relaxation of the neck of the gallbladder, force bile out into the duodenum⁸.

ANOMALIES AND ANATOMIC VARIATIONS

Gallbladder agenesis

It is caused by developmental failure of the caudal division of the primitive hepatic diverticulum or vacuolization failure after the solid phase of embryonic development. Atresia or hypoplasia of the gallbladder represents aborted development of the organ⁹⁻¹⁰.

On ultrasound, a linear echogenic area is seen in gallbladder fossa due to dense fibrous tissue.

On ultrasound, gallbladder was not visualized, but strong echoes with acoustic shadowing were seen¹¹.

Duplication of the gallbladder

It is caused by incomplete revacuolization of the primitive gallbladder, resulting in a persistent longitudinal septum that divides the gallbladder lengthwise. Another mechanism is the development of two cystic buds separately.

To establish the diagnosis, two separate gallbladder cavities, each with its own cystic duct must be present. These two cystic ducts may separately enter common duct or form a Y configuration before a common entrance¹¹.

On ultrasound, two cystic structures will be seen in region of gallbladder fossa which are connected to a common cystic duct or two separate cystic ducts that lead to a common hepatic duct ¹².

In 2002, Lisa L et al, Sonographic Detection of Gallbladder Duplication;

On ultrasound 2 fluid-containing structures adjacent to the fetal liver were seen. These were saccular in morphology and were situated in the same plane. A small rim of tissue was noted between them. Duplicated gallbladder was diagnosed ¹³.

Phrygiancap

Deformity is characterized by a fold or septum of the gallbladder between the body and fundus. Two variations can be seen. In the retroserosal type, the peritoneum smoothly invests the gallbladder, and the mucosal fold that projects into the lumen may not be visible externally. In the serosal type the peritoneum follows the bend in the fundus, reflects on itself as the fundus overlies the body ¹⁴.

Easily visualized **on ultrasound** as asymptomatic folding of the gallbladder fundus over body ¹⁵.

Multiseptate Gallbladder

Characterized by multiple septations of different sizes internally and a faintly bosselated surface externally ¹⁶⁻¹⁹.

These septations cause stasis of bile and gallstone formation.

On ultrasound studies, multiple communicating septa and locules are seen bridging the gallbladder lumen ²⁰.

On ultrasound distended gallbladder with a thickened wall. There was also a transverse septum which divided the gallbladder into two cavities. No calculi were seen and the common bile duct was within normal limits²¹.

Diverticula

Gallbladder diverticula are rare and most of the times clinically asymptomatic. No site of predilection in the gallbladder and are usually single and are of varying sizes.

Congenital diverticula are true diverticula and contain all the layers of wall, on the contrary pseudodiverticula of adenomyomatosis, have no smooth muscle component in their walls²².

On ultrasound, local outpouching of the entire gallbladder wall with a narrow neck is seen²³.

In 2009, Selim Doganay et al, True Diverticulum of the Gallbladder; **Abdominal Ultrasound** depicted a local outpouching of the entire gallbladder wall with a narrow neck, diagnostic of true diverticulum; its diameter was approximately 25 mm, and a little biliary sludge in the lumen of the gallbladder was also present. The wall of the gallbladder was mildly thickened (4 mm). No evidence of gallstone. MRCP confirmed, true diverticulum with dilatation of the intrahepatic biliary ducts²⁴.

Wandering Gallbladder

When the gallbladder has an unusually long mesentery, it can "float " or "wander"²⁵⁻²⁹.

The gallbladder may "disappear" into the pelvis or may be seen in front of the spine or to the left of the abdomen. Rarely, it can be seen herniating through the foramen of Winslow into the lesser sac.

Ectopic Gallbladder

The gallbladder can be seen in a various anomalous positions; Intrahepatic, suprahepatic, retrohepatic, supradiaphragmatic, and retroperitoneal, can also be seen in the transverse mesocolon, falciform ligament, and anterior abdominal wall.

In patients with cirrhosis, small or absent right lobes, or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, the gallbladder together with the colon is interposed between the diaphragm and the liver³⁰.

Left-sided gallbladder location is seen in situs inversustotalis. Gallbladder in the left upper quadrant without situs inversus is even more rare. Intrahepatic gallbladders are relocated in subcapsular region in the anterior inferior right lobe of the liver. This leads to problem for scintigraphy, as an intrahepatic gallbladder can cause a focal defect; sonography is helpful in these cases³¹⁻³².

On ultrasound neck of the gallbladder is seen anterior to the right branch of the portal vein helps in identification of gallbladder³³.

For confirmation the patients were given food with high fat. Decrease in the size of the cystic area was noted after repeating the ultrasound examination after two hours of intake of fatty meal indicating the contraction of ectopic gallbladder.

PATHOLOGIES

Acute cholecystitis

In 2014, Hamish Hwang et al, in the article Does acute cholecystitis can be diagnosed accurately by ultrasonography? Improving diagnostic accuracy based on a study at a regional hospital, in 107 patients, found that ultrasonography had 100% sensitivity, 18% specificity, 81% positive predictive value (PPV) and 100% negative predictive value (NPV) for cholelithiasis.

In case of acute cholecystitis, sensitivity was 54%, specificity of 81%, 85% PPV and 47% NPV. For chronic cholecystitis the sensitivity was found to be 100% with ultrasonography³⁴.

In 2011, Aldo Benjamim Rodrigues Barbosa et al, in Gallbladder wall thickening at ultrasonography: how to interpret it? cholecystitis considered responsible for the wall thickening found in only eight patients. The rest had hepatitis, alcoholic liver disease with hypoproteinemia, heart failure, renal disease, and multiple myeloma; however, all lacked clinical evidence of biliary disease. Diagnosis of cholecystitis only on the basis of wall thickening alone should be cautious³⁵.

In 2010, Oliveira GA et al, Transient reticular gallbladder wall thickening in severe dengue fever: a reliable sign of plasma leakage; Flavivirus is responsible for acute infection, **Dengue fever (DF)**. Mild symptoms were seen in most of the patients; only few progressed to a severe form characterized by hypovolemic shock and hemorrhagic phenomena. Plasma leakage was characteristically observed in severe form of DF.

Ultrasound triad of plasma leakage in DF include wall thickening, ascites and pleural effusion.

Abdominal ultrasound examination was done in 37 children with severe DF on first day of admission at the time of discharge and on 7th day after the first examination if the child was still hospitalized.

Of the 37 children, 33 (89.2%) presented gallbladder wall thickening, 29 (78.4%) ascites and 26 (70.3%) pleural effusion. By the time of second examination, most of the findings had resolved. Of the 33 gallbladder wall thickenings, reticular pattern of presentation was characteristic of plasma leakage in patients with severe DF in 29 (87.9%).

Gallbladder wall thickening, pleural effusion and ascites were reactive findings in DF. They concluded that acalculous cholecystitis should not be diagnosed on the basis of typical reticular pattern of gallbladder wall thickening but, they can be used to diagnose and follow up of patients with severe DF³⁶.

In 2007, van Breda Vriesman AC et al, studied on diffuse gallbladder wall thickening; When there is clinical suspicion of acute cholecystitis ultrasound is generally the preferred initial imaging technique. The sensitivity of ultrasound ranges from 80% to 100% and specificity is 60% to 100%. Imaging findings may include gallstones, gallbladder wall thickening (of more than 3-5 mm), pericholecystic fluid, and positive sonographic Murphy sign. Gallstone within the gallbladder neck or cystic duct, distended gallbladder and echogenic sludge are other less-specific findings.

Gallbladder wall thickening with positive sonographic Murphy's sign and cholelithiasis increased diagnostic accuracy of acute cholecystitis.

There was increase in PPV for acute cholecystitis by 4% when combination of gallstones and positive sonographic Murphy's sign to 92% from 88% with gallstones alone³⁷.

In 2006, Kane MA et al, Ultrasound findings in acute viral hepatitis: 177 acute viral hepatitis patients which were clinical diagnosed were studied from Jun 2004 - 2006. 32 patients were excluded, 145 patients which were serologically confirmed with uncomplicated acute viral hepatitis were studied.

Sonography was done after overnight fasting in supine position on all patients.

USG was repeated after 3-4 weeks. Collapsed gallbladder with increased wall thickness was most common findings seen in more than 50% of all types of hepatitis. These findings were seen in all patients with HAV hepatitis and in 84% cases of Hepatitis E. 4 to 18 mm were wall thickness range. Liver enzymes were elevated proportionally as the gallbladder wall thickness increased. 51% of Hepatitis E patients showed pericholecystic oedema. Associated sludge was seen in less than 50%. High transaminase levels accounts for more gallbladder ultrasound findings. However, these ultrasound findings were temporarily seen and in most of the patients, findings disappeared within 3 weeks of the first ultrasound examination.

They concluded that ultrasound findings were seen in more than 80% of hepatitis patients with enteric route of transmission. As a result when biochemical tests are not available ultrasound can be used to diagnose acute hepatitis³⁸.

In 1995, M.L. Kulkarni et al, studied on Acute Acalculous Cholecystitis in Typhoid Fever, they conducted in a study of 50 patients with typhoid fever examined by Sonography.

Out of 50 patients, 30 were culture positive and remaining had characteristic signs and symptoms with Widal test positive ('O' titre > 1:160). All patients were subjected to abdominal sonography in fasting state. 4 (8%) patients were diagnosed of acalculous cholecystitis. 3 out of 4 children presented during the first week of illness.

The Ultrasound criteria for acute acalculous cholecystitis include a thickened gallbladder wall (more than 3 mm), sonographic Murphy's sign, a round shape, pericholecystic collection and the absence of gallstones. Sonography was repeated at weekly intervals, showed normal appearance after 3 weeks to 3 months. Rarely cholecystectomy was required in cases of acalculous cholecystitis with associated suppuration, ischemia or septic complications. They concluded acalculous cholecystitis, frequent complication was detected frequently in typhoid fever³⁹.

Gangrenous cholecystitis

Gallbladder is mainly supplied by cystic artery. In case of embolism, arteriosclerosis is the usual abnormality which occurs as a result of occlusion/stenosis of cystic artery leading to compromised viability of the gallbladder. Vascular insufficiency is the main cause of emphysematous cholecystitis, with associated diabetes mellitus, predominance in males, high frequency of gangrene, and occurrence in older patients. Vascular compromise of the cystic artery results in ischemia of the gallbladder and facilitates the growth of gas-forming organisms (eg, **Clostridium or Escherichia coli**) and bacterial proliferation in the devitalized tissue with low oxygen saturation.

Among anaerobic organisms, **Bacteroides fragilis** were most frequently isolated. High rate of isolation of anaerobic bacteria from bile in patients with

gangrenous cholecystitis (72%). Bactericidal bile is rendered alkaline, facilitating infection of the bile.

In 2015, Teena Dhira et al, Old man gallbladder syndrome: Gangrenous cholecystitis in unsuspected patients; Gangrenous cholecystitis (GC) is a rare but fulminant complication of acute cholecystitis. The pathophysiology of ischemia and necrosis of the gallbladder occurs secondary to distended gallbladder with increased tension and pressure on the gallbladder wall.

Acute cholecystitis complicating to gangrenous cholecystitis is a common surgical condition. Increased postoperative complications, morbidity and mortality were seen in gangrenous cholecystitis. Predictive factors for gangrenous cholecystitis include age more than 45, male predominance, WBC count more than $13,000/\text{mm}^3$ and **negative sonographic Murphy's sign.**

The incidence of gangrenous cholecystitis was 2% to 30% in patients with acute cholecystitis and has been seen commonly in elderly patients. The risk of gangrenous cholecystitis was also increased in patients with a history of diabetes.

Ultrasound findings predictive of GC include increased wall thickness along with elevated WBC. Positive predictive findings of GC include findings of discontinuous and/ or irregular mucosal enhancement pattern, and it was found that the lack of mural enhancement was statistically significant correlating to gangrenous cholecystitis along with gallbladder distension and wall thickening of $>4.0\text{--}4.5$ mm. Other findings that help predict gangrenous cholecystitis include perforation of gallbladder, pericholecystic stranding and a **sonographic Murphy's sign negative.**

The reasoning for a negative Murphy's sign, due to denervation of the gallbladder, decreasing the suspicion for a more pathological process. Due to the transmural necrosis of the gallbladder wall, the afferent nerves die and the inflammation spreads to the parietal peritoneum, leading to generalized abdominal pain.

They concluded that gangrenous cholecystitis a fulminant form of acute cholecystitis with associated increased morbidity, mortality and worse postoperative outcomes. Risk factors for GC including age > 45 years, male gender, WBC > 13,000/mm³, ultrasound and CT findings of irregular gallbladders with lack of mural enhancement and were later found to have GC. Though the finding of GC does not change the surgical management of disease, knowing that a patient is at increased risk of GC should prompt earlier surgical intervention to prevent some of the known complications from this disease³⁹.

In 1991, Teefey SA et al, Gangrenous cholecystitis: new observations on ultrasound; ultrasound findings suggestive of gangrenous change include floating intraluminal membranes, echogenic foci with shadowing consistent with gas within the gallbladder wall/lumen, frank defect of the gallbladder wall and abscess formation in pericholecystic area. Characteristic diagnostic sign of gangrenous cholecystitis is striations of gallbladder wall, or presence of alternating hyperechoic and hypoechoic mural linear areas seen in up to 40% of patients⁴⁰.

Emphysematous cholecystitis

In 2002, Konno K et al, Emphysematous cholecystitis: sonographic findings were assessed; Acute cholecystitis rarely complicates with emphysematous cholecystitis (EC) early diagnosis is necessary to prevent management delay.

Comparison was done with clinical and ultrasound features of 11 surgically proven cases of EC (with minimal amounts of gas in three cases and large amounts in eight cases).

In cases with minimal amounts of gas, sonography showed a hyperechoic line with a distinct ring-down artifact or a "powder snow-like" speckled posterior shadowing, with increased amounts of gas, a wide spiculated echogenic band with a powder snow-like speckled posterior shadowing. Gallbladder wall was not visualized in all cases due to presence of gas. Differentiation of gas localized to the gallbladder wall and gas extending to the surrounding hepatic tissue was not possible by sonography. Gas was seen throughout the intrahepatic bile ducts in 2 diabetic cases^{41,42}.

Perforation of gallbladder

In 2006, Derici et al⁴³, Diagnosis and treatment of gallbladder perforation; gallbladder perforation is an important complication of gangrenous cholecystitis. Gall-bladder perforation is caused by transmural necrosis in a case of acute cholecystitis.

2–11% of cases of acute uncomplicated cholecystitis gradually progress to perforation, with a reported mortality rate of up to 60%. After perforation, patients got significantly reduced from pain. Perforation is classified into three types. Type I perforation involves spillage of gallbladder intraluminal contents into the peritoneal cavity, type II perforation is subacute process with an adjacent abscess formation. Type III perforation is a chronic process with the formation of a cholecysto-enteric fistula⁴⁴. Fundus of gallbladder is the most common site of perforation. **Gallbladder wall shows a focal defect on ultrasound, CT or MRI. An extraluminal gallstone is**

a characteristic imaging finding that indicates perforation. Features of perforation are nonspecific and include pericholecystic fluid, luminal collapse of gallbladder and abscess in pericholecystic area⁴⁵.

Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis

In 2015, Hideki Suzuki et al⁴⁶, studied on Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis (XGC): Difficult to differentiate from carcinoma of gallbladder; XGC is a rare form of chronic cholecystitis, seen in 1.3% to 5.2% of resected gallbladder specimens.

From Apr 2000 to Dec 2013, in 6 patients of XGC extended surgical resection was done. 16 patients were proved with carcinoma gallbladder, according to extended surgical resection. Only XGC cases were chosen for study having indistinct borders with the liver in most of the situations it is difficult to distinguish these patients from advanced carcinoma gallbladder. Comparison with ultrasound findings, clinical feature and computed tomography findings between XGC and advanced carcinoma gallbladder. Clinical features like age, gender, symptoms and tumor markers were retrospectively assessed.

The CT findings were used to compare two conditions, to detect the co-existing gallstones, pattern of gallbladder wall thickening (focal/diffuse), the presence of a hypodense intramural nodule and continuation of the mucosal line.

Preoperative evaluation was carried out with ultrasound, CT, MRI and FDG-PET.

Ultrasound features of Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis include gross gallbladder wall thickening with oval hypoechoic nodules⁴⁷. Kim et al⁴⁸

suggested the combination of diffuse wall thickening and ultrasound findings and nodular wall thickening are highly suggestive of Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis.

67% of patients presented with abdominal pain with Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis, however, there were no major differences in clinical symptoms, including fever, between the two groups.

83% of patients had cholelithiasis with XGC, when compared to carcinoma gallbladder it was 33%. Hypodense intramural nodule was seen in 3 patients with Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis (3/6, 50%), but in only 1 patient with carcinoma gallbladder (1/16, 6%). The gallbladder wall thickness, continuous mucosal line, and dilatation of bile duct were not significantly different between Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis and carcinoma gallbladder.

The macroscopic features of Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis include abnormal gallbladder wall thickening with irregular soft to firm, yellow-brown various sized nodules within wall with cholecystitis. Complications include gallbladder perforation, abscess formation, cholecystoduodenal fistula and spread of inflammation to adjacent liver and transverse colon⁴⁹. Involvement of adjacent organs suggests aggressive nature of Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis, as does advanced carcinoma gallbladder. Thus it is important to differentiate Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis from advanced carcinoma gallbladder preoperatively to avoid unnecessary surgery.

The clinical features of Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis are of acute or chronic cholecystitis. The primary symptoms include pain in right hypochondriac region (93.9%) radiating to shoulder and back pain (42.4%), fever (24.2%), nausea (33.3%) and vomiting (24.2%). Patients with Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis

more commonly presents with pain abdomen jaundice and fever in comparison with carcinoma gallbladder⁵⁰. Excluding features like weight loss or features of ascites or metastases in advanced carcinoma gallbladder, clinically it is difficult to differentiate between these two conditions.

The mechanism behind Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis is initially biliary obstruction with acute or chronic cholecystitis and increasing intraluminal pressure, followed by a granulomatous reaction.

Obstruction to normal flow of bile causes granulation reaction that leads to the formation of intramural nodules as a result of extravasation into the gallbladder wall through a small ulceration in the mucosa with involvement of the Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses⁵¹.

The radiological features of Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis and carcinoma of gallbladder, like gallbladder wall thickening and involvement of neighboring organs are nearly similar. However, Uchiyama et al⁵² stated that continuous enhancement of mucosal line is characteristic for Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis. Cholelithiasis adds more to the diagnosis of Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis. In their study, cholelithiasis was seen more commonly with Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis in comparison to carcinoma gallbladder.

They concluded that pseudotumoral Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis has led to difficulty in terms of surgery. Even with advanced imaging techniques it is difficult to differentiate between Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis and malignant lesions of gallbladder. Macroscopically also it was difficult to differentiate between Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis from carcinoma gallbladder when Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis is seen with irregular growth and involving

adjacent organs. Hence carcinoma radical resection including liver gallbladder is justified as Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis and malignancy cannot be completely excluded.

In 2000, Parra JA et al, Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis: studied on clinical, ultrasound, and CT findings in 26 patients; rare inflammatory disorder characterized by abnormal nodules within gallbladder wall⁵³. Rokitansky–Aschoff sinuses become occluded and rupture resulting in formation of intra mural nodules. Bile is then forced into the gallbladder wall causing an inflammatory reaction, which is comprised of histiocytes, multinucleated giant cells and fibroblasts. Superadded infection is most frequently seen in elderly patients.

Gallstones and thickened GB wall are frequent features on sonography and CT, in patients with Xanthogranulomatous cholecystitis. Wall thickening may be segmental or diffuse. Pericholecystic inflammatory reactions are seen.

Intramural hypoechoic on ultrasound or hypoattenuating nodules on CT or bands are diagnostic of XGC⁵⁴.

Cholelithiasis

Bile is synthesized in liver transported to gallbladder for storage and is concentrated, gets emptied into duodenum which helps in breakdown of fats. Not all cases are symptomatic. However, cholecystitis results due to obstructed stone within the bile duct or gallbladder.

There are three types of gallstones

Cholesterol (10%)

More than 50% cholesterol contents; form with excessive concentration of bile, nucleation and growth of calculus

Mixed (80%)

20-50% cholesterol is causative agent as seen with cholesterol calculi

Pigment stones (10%)

Contains less than 20% cholesterol; has high bilirubin component and occur when there is concentration of unconjugated bilirubin

Pigment stones are divided into,

Black pigment stones: due to hemolytic anemias, liver cirrhosis, intestinal malabsorption (ex; Crohn disease)

Brown pigment stones: bacterial & parasitic inclusions (ex; Clonorchis sinensis) and stasis of bile.

In 2014, Yen-Chun Chen et al⁵⁵, studied on The Prevalence and Risk Factors for gallstone disease in Taiwanese Vegetarians; The of load gallstone disease (GSD) and its problems, including cholecystitis, pancreatitis and cholangitis, are major health problems globally. Many sufferers with gallstone disease are asymptomatic and around 20% become symptomatic after 10 years of record. Ultrasound is first modality for diagnosing gallstone disease⁵⁶.

It was observed in 425 males and 1296 females vegetarians who were showing willingness for the study.

The diagnosis of gallstone disease was confirmed by ultrasound. In their study, there was no sex predilection and there was weak association of increasing age with gallstone disease. Incidence of gallstone disease in male and female vegetarians is similar in this study.

Body mass index is weakly associated with gallstone disease in females. Gender is accounted as a risk factor for gallstone disease. Few Asian studies have proved slightly higher incidence of gallstone disease in women but not as high as in Western populations. Pregnancy also plays significant role in gallstone disease. After delivery few cases showed disappearance of sludge and gallstones⁵⁷. In this study, increased total bilirubin levels were considerably associated with gallstone disease in male vegetarians in comparison to females. They proposed that the increased probability for gallstone disease in veg population vary with gender. Increasing age is a main and collective risk factor for gallstone disease. Increased total bilirubin levels and body mass index also appeared to be risk factors in male and females correspondingly⁵⁸.

In 2012, Laura M. Stinton et al, in analysis of gallbladder pathologies in defined population: gallstones and carcinoma, affirmed as common pathologies and reveal as cholelithiasis and carcinoma gallbladder. Ultrasound being noninvasive and non ionizing radiation, is gold standard to determine precisely the occurrence of cholelithiasis and can precisely distinguish the occurrence of cholelithiasis in a given asymptomatic group of subjects.

Today ultrasound examination is widely in use to study GB pathologies at any point in contrast to clinical or necropsy based evidence previously. Hazardous triggers like severe obesity, losing weight quickly, inactive way of life and mainly nutritional factors which can be modified should be recognized and offer a chance to avoid gallstones. Some of the causatives responsible for cholelithiasis are concerned with carcinoma gallbladder pathogenesis⁵⁹.

Gallbladder polyp

In 2015, Vincent M Mellnick et al, studied on Polyp like Lesions of the GB: Disease variety with Pathologic Correspondence, Gallbladder polyps are defined as sessile projections of the gallbladder wall into the lumen⁶⁰. They are typically incidentally found at ultrasound. Unlike gallstones, gallbladder polyps are not significantly associated with female sex, obesity or multiparity.

Gallbladder polyps are quite frequent, incidence is 3%–7% at abdominal ultrasound and 2%–12% in cholecystectomy specimens. A wide array of pseudotumors, as well as benign and malignant tumors, may manifest as gallbladder polyps. By far, most gallbladder polyps are benign. Since malignant lesions can be resectable for cure, early detection is of crucial importance.

Ultrasound findings used to stratify gallbladder polyps into three groups: those that need no further follow-up, those that require follow-up, and those that should be excised (i.e, cholecystectomy).

Ultrasound protocols should include multiplanar gray-scale images, as well as color and spectral Doppler images of detected lesions. Lesions should be imaged in more than one position (e.g. supine and left decubitus) to avoid mistaking mobile

sludge balls for polypoid lesions. It is important to note the size and shape (e.g. pedunculated or sessile) of a polypoid lesion and the presence of gallstones, which increase the likelihood, that the polyp is a neoplastic lesion. Other findings include gallbladder wall thickening adjacent to the polypoid lesion, multiple polyps, biliary strictures and hepatic masses. The presence of twinkling artifact may help diagnose adenomyomatosis.

The cholesterol polyp is by far the most common polypoid lesion found in the gallbladder, accounting for 60%–70% of lesions in some studies. It predominantly occurs in middle-aged women. Cholesterol polyps are typically multiple and need not be associated with gallstones. No risk of carcinogenesis from cholesterol polyps. Ultrasound, these sizes are not of worrisome, round, smoothly contoured, intraluminal lesions that are attached to the wall. The stalk is rarely seen, an appearance that gives rise to the “ball on the wall” sign. Cholesterol polyps are usually echogenic with no acoustic shadowing; however, particularly when multiple cholesterol polyps are confluent and/or larger than 1 cm, they cannot be definitively differentiated from other benign or malignant lesions at imaging.

In 2011, Michael T. Corwin et al, Incidentally Detected Gallbladder Polyps: Is Follow-up Necessary? studied on 346 patients, GB polyps are incidentally detected in around 4 to 7% where gallbladder ultrasound was done.

Main apprehension was progression to malignancy like adenocarcinoma, since the lesions were recognized as neoplastic. Risk of malignancy is more in polyps of 1 cm or more diameter, single polyp, sessile polyps, polyps with adjoining increased wall thickness and also with increasing age.

When two or more polyps were recognized and increase in size of 0.2 cm or more on follow-up study it was of significance. They were distinguished as stable, resolved, increased/reduced in size on the basis of the highest length measurement.

They studied on 346 patients with mean age of 52 yrs (20–93 years). 156 were males and 190 females 45% & 55% respectively. 216 patients showed single polyp and were multiple in 130 patients. Range was 1 to 1.8 cm with a mean size of 0.5 cm +/- 2.4. 30 patients showed associated gallstones i.e., 9%. On 149 patients 43% ultrasound follow up study was done. In 90 patients i.e., 60% polyp size was unchanged, in eight patients i.e., 5% size was reduced, in only 1 patient <1% increased dimension was seen and resolved in 50 patients i.e., 34%. 42 patients (12%) undergone with resection of gallbladder, of which 13 i.e., 31% had polyps, 24 (57%) with cholelithiasis and no polyps, and five (12%) with neither a cholelithiasis nor polyp. None were recognized with carcinoma gallbladder out of 346 subjects. Mean polyp size was 0.5 cm (1–1.8 cm). Between 0.1–0.6 cm no neoplasticity was identified, 1 polyp between 0.7–0.9 cm was neoplastic and 2 neoplastic polyps were found at 1 cm or more.

They concluded that, even further evaluation or follow up is also not necessary in cases where polyp size is <0.6 cm and risk of carcinogenesis is exceptionally low⁶¹.

In 2002, D Chattopadhyay et al, in result of gallbladder polypoidal lesions detected by abdominal sonography: 9 yr study conducted and assessment of all patients who underwent sonography who were referred to gastrointestinal surgeon at district health centre. They included all subjects with polyp like lesions in gallbladder. Out of 651, 23 pts were recognised by sonography to have a polyp like lesions prior to surgery. Post surgical resection microscopic study revealed 12 cases with

cholelithiasis, 7 cases as polyps of cholesterol, 3 adenocarcinomas within polyps and one normal gallbladder.

Ultrasound is 92% specific for recognizing polyp like lesions. In general ultrasound has 66 % sensitivity, is 100% specific in suspicion of carcinoma prior to surgery. All the true polyps were malignant. Ultrasound showed 100% sensitivity and 87 % specificity with a PPV of 50% in the diagnosis of malignancy in polyp like lesions, when size of polyp is taken 1 cm as cut-off. Most of the patients with polyp like lesions shown to have associated cholelithiasis. When polyps of more than 1 cm are encountered on ultrasound additional studies like endoscopic ultrasound/CT/MR were suggested⁶².

Adenomyomatosis

In 2006, Alexis R. Boscak et al, studied on Adenomyomatosis of the Gallbladder: is a benign hyperplastic cholecystosis, frequently identified, in at least 5% of surgical GB specimens, also called as adenomyomatous hyperplasia of the GB. There is no definite ethnic/sex based increased occurrence⁶³.

Gallbladder wall has four layers: mucosa, lamina propria, muscularis propria, serosa; there is no muscularis mucosa/submucosa. Mechanism of development of adenomyomatosis is overgrowth of mucosa, muscularis propria layers. It has been named as “strawberry gallbladder” due to gross appearance which is the result of cholesterolosis, due to accumulation of triglycerides and cholesterol esters in lamina propria. Bile gets accumulated in Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses, which are small outpouchings occurring within wall lined by mucosa, and as a result cholesterol gets increasingly collected in the gallbladder lumen.

Adenomyomatosis is inconsistent and degree of involvement, site and varying sonographic forms such as diffuse, segmental, and focal are encountered.

Focal form is more frequently seen as hemispherical to rounded thickened GB wall, commonly at the fundus. Generalized form shows extensive involvement of gallbladder. Segmental/annular form seen as incomplete circumferentially involving the wall causing stenosis of lumen within the body of gallbladder, attributing to hourglass formation. **Ruling out of malignancy** is challenging in annular and localized cases; actually, localized form look as distinct mass, called adenomyoma. Metabolic categorization with fluorine 18 FDG PET is helpful add-on in difficult cases.

They concluded that adenomyomatous hyperplasia is fairly frequent benign gallbladder pathology with characteristic gross and microscopic characters relating to comparatively **precise characteristics at ultrasound**. Cholecystectomy is indicated in problematic cases⁶⁴.

In 2006 J. Carvajal Balaguera et al, diffuse adenomyomatosis of the gallbladder: uncommon entity with strenuous exercise to diagnose prior to surgery; It is uncommon entity of the gallbladder with features of thickening of muscular layer of gallbladder wall due to epithelial proliferation resulting in pouch formation within gallbladder wall also known as Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses. Many subjects are clinically silent hence the condition is detected secondarily due to sonography done for other symptoms.

Adenomyomatous hyperplasia is an uncommon condition of unknown etiology which grows slowly. It can involve any site within gallbladder, frequently seen at fundus and rarely seen in the biliary tree. Since patients are clinically silent,

detection is not easy. In cases of clinically active lesions they mimic cholelithiasis. Sonography and CT are helpful in reaching the diagnosis.

Out of 11, 9 cases were seen in the fundus of gallbladder, 1 in cystic duct, 1 in distal CBD, rarely it is seen in right and left hepatic ducts, CHD & hepatopancreatic duct. Further it can also be seen in stomach, small intestine, Meckel's diverticulum, sigmoid colon, recti muscles, uterus, uterine supports, ovary, abdominal cavity and also related with Gardner syndrome.

Thickened gallbladder wall of more than 5 mm, herniation of mucosa into muscular layer forming pouches named as Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses, distended lumen and sluggish growth are the characteristic features. Its patho-physiology is analogous to colon diverticulosis⁶⁵. Histopathologically, it is characterized by a rapid growth of flat muscular fibres and epithelial adenomatous cells. Based on their site of involvement and varied ultrasound appearances, 3 forms have been described: Focal 48%, diffuse 26% and segmental form 26%⁶⁶. Mixed forms are also recognized⁶⁷.

Conditions like in 89% gallstones & chronic cholecystitis, in 22% choledocholithiasis and in 22% with previous history of pancreatitis of biliary origin, were commonly associated (81%) with adenomyomatous hyperplasia. Hence, they infer persistent inflammation of the biliary mucosa is recognized as etiological factor⁶⁸. Rarely it is seen related to GB adenocarcinoma or leiomyosarcoma⁶⁹⁻⁷², to congenital defects of the biliary tree or to duodenal diverticula⁷³. Nabatame et al⁷⁴ stated that annular form of adenomatous hyperplasia is associated with increased risk of carcinoma GB (6.6%) with increasing age (15.6%). These tumours have also been called as adenomyosis, hamartomas or hyperplastic adenomyomatosis⁷⁵.

GB adenomyomatosis affects men and women between 40 and 70 years in similar proportion. Peak incidence is around 50 years. Occasionally it is also seen in pediatric population^{76,77}.

Diagnosis prior to surgery is complex as there is no clinical suspicion and is seen in several forms in function of the localization. Qiao et al⁷⁸ accounted that only in seven out of 42 cases it was diagnosed accurately prior to surgery. Clinically patients may be silent (60%)¹⁰⁰ or present with vague symptoms. These symptoms can be: indigestion, right hypochondriac pain, PUO, acute/chronic cholecystitis⁷⁹. When it involves biliary tree, it can cause symptoms of extrahepatic cholestasis, hemobilia, cholangitis or pancreatitis. Specifically an adenomyoma of the cystic duct presents with colicky pain and gallbladder hydrops⁸⁰.

Patients with generalized adenomyomatous hyperplasia, **ultrasound feature** thickened wall with tiny outpouches indicating the Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses. Annular type manifests analogous to cholecystitis.

In tiny and plane lesions, ultrasound was unable to distinguish between benign and malignant lesions⁸¹.

They concluded that adenomyomatous hyperplasia is infrequent and patients are clinically silent and when presents with symptoms, they are similar to cholecystopathy. Since there is no suspicion, diagnosis prior to surgery is worrisome and is found incidentally most of the times on ultrasound. Surgical excision is widely accepted management because of indefinite evolution of this entity.

In 1983 Raghavendra BN et al, Sonography of adenomyomatosis of the gallbladder: radiologic-pathologic correlation; Adenomyomatosis seen in 9% of post

surgical specimens and accounts for about 25% of polyp like lesions of GB¹⁰⁴. The focal form of adenomyomatosis may be seen as a fundal polypoid lesion **at ultrasound**. The segmental form typically affects the body, demonstrates concentric circumferential wall thickening and may give rise to an hourglass configuration of the gallbladder.

Imaging findings of adenomyomatosis parallels its histologic features: intramural diverticula that may be filled with inspissated bile and appear as multiple small cystic spaces that are anechoic **at ultrasound**. When the intramural diverticula contains sludge, stones or papillary projections, they appear echogenic with multiple acoustic interfaces at ultrasound, creating twinkling or comet-tail artifacts⁸². The cystic spaces may be visible at CT, which can help differentiate between fundal, adenomyomatosis and gallbladder carcinoma⁸³.

They concluded that adenomyomatous hyperplasia of the GB should be suspected when (a) generalized or annular GB wall thickening and (b) outpouchings within GB wall are seen as anechoic or hyperechoic areas with or without associated acoustic shadows or reverberation artifacts.

Carcinoma gallbladder

In 2008, M Barbhuiya, T Singh, S Gupta, B Shrivastav, P Tiwari, in Incidence of gallbladder cancer in rural and semi-urban population of north central India.

They collected information on the medical diagnosis and demographics of all the 464 different categories of gallbladder disease patients who were admitted for treatment during the above period. Out of 464 patients, 365 had GBC with Gallstone (abbreviated as GSC onwards), 15 had Gallstone (abbreviated as GS), 36 with

Gallbladder Cancer without stone (abbreviated as GC), 30 with Chronic Cholecystitis (abbreviated as CC) and 18 having Gallbladder Cancer with Cholecystitis (abbreviated as GCC). They excluded the data of patients who left the hospital after check- up at outpatient door for personal problems and studied all the comparative data available from the hospital record for those who got admitted and properly diagnosed. The cases were confirmed on the basis of clinical investigations, like X-ray, ultrasound, cytological examination (FNAC), histopathological examination and blood biochemistry reports. About 80% of the diagnosis is based on the ultrasound, chest X-ray and cytological tests (FNAC) and of remaining 20%, after post surgical histopathology. Sample t- test was carried out for the average values of the parameters in five different categories of gallbladder disease (collectively abbreviated as GBD). A total of 419 gallbladder cancer (abbreviated as GBC) with or without gallstones/ cholecystitis were included in the present study. The statistical analysis was performed using Graph Pad Prisma problem in the diagnosis and treatment.

Gallbladder Cancer was the fourth most common cancer constituting about 11% of patients admitted at the hospital ⁸⁴.

In 2007, Randi Get al, Gallbladder carcinoma:found that cholelithiasis is an important risk factor for the development of gallbladder cancer. Up to 95% of gallbladder cancers are associated with gallstones. They conducted cohort study, the relative risk of developing gallbladder cancer in patients with gallstone disease was 8.3 compared to the general population. Case control studies also confirmed the association between cholelithiasis and gallbladder cancer with relative risks ranging widely from 2.3 to 34.4 between different studies. There also appears to be an association between gallstone size and the risk of developing gallbladder cancer.

Patients with gallstones larger than 3 cm have an approximately 10-fold higher risk of developing gallbladder cancer.

Elevated body mass index and multiparity are also correlated with an increased risk of developing gallbladder cancer. Cohort study including over two million people and 1715 cases of gallbladder cancer showed a relative risk of developing gallbladder cancer of 2.53 for women aged 20-44 years patients with a body mass index greater than 30.

Salmonella infection is an important causative factor in the pathogenesis of gallbladder cancer. The most compelling evidence was from a cohort study based on a typhoid outbreak where 507 cases of typhoid or paratyphoid were reported.

Gallbladder cancer has three distinct appearances on ultrasound: (1) a mass replacing the gallbladder or invading the gallbladder bed, (2) an intraluminal gallbladder growth or polyp, or (3) asymmetric gallbladder wall thickening. In cases of locally advanced disease, USG has a sensitivity of 85% and an overall accuracy of 80% in diagnosing gallbladder cancer. However, in earlier lesions, especially where the tumor or cancerous polyp is flat or sessile and is associated with cholelithiasis, ultrasound examination can fail to detect the lesion. In a series of 71 patients with early gallbladder cancer, ultrasound had a sensitivity of 53% for sessile tumors. Color Doppler ultrasound may assist in diagnosis as detection of higher flow within a lesion has been reported to correlate with malignancy. Besides ascertaining the diagnosis of cancer, ultrasound is also useful in staging the disease by defining the extent of biliary tree involvement as well as confirming the presence of hepatic arterial or portal venous invasion⁸⁵.

In 2007 Alessandro Furlan et al, Gallbladder Carcinoma Update: Multimodality Imaging Evaluation, Staging, and Treatment Options.

In cases of suspected gallbladder disease, sonography is often the first imaging technique because of its relatively low cost and widespread availability.

Gallbladder carcinoma appear as a mass completely occupying or replacing the gallbladder lumen, focal or diffuse asymmetric gallbladder wall thickening, or an intraluminal polypoid lesion⁸⁶.

Mass Occupying or Replacing the Gallbladder Lumen, this pattern is seen in 40–65% of patients with gallbladder carcinoma at initial detection. On ultrasound the presence of a large gallbladder mass that nearly fills or replaces the lumen, often directly invading the surrounding liver parenchyma, is highly suggestive of gallbladder carcinoma. On ultrasound heterogeneous, predominantly hypoechoic tumor fills much or all of the gallbladder lumen. Anechoic foci of trapped bile or necrotic tumor may be present, as well as echogenic shadowing foci from gallstones, porcelain gallbladder, or tumor calcifications.

The initial detection of gallbladder carcinoma as a polypoid lesion occurs in 15–25% of cases. Malignant lesions are usually larger than 1 cm in diameter and may have a thickened implantation base. The differential diagnosis of a polypoid gallbladder lesion includes adenomatous or hyperplastic cholesterol polyps as well as uncommon tumors such as carcinoid or metastases such as melanoma. At ultrasound, if movement of a polypoid mass occurs with a change of the patient's position, then a pseudotumor of biliary sludge or clot can be diagnosed.

It is imperative to closely scrutinize the gallbladder, particularly in patients who are at increased risk of developing gallbladder carcinoma, for subtle morphologic abnormalities that indicate cancer. Recognition of the characteristic imaging appearances of primary gallbladder carcinoma and understanding its pathways of spread and staging criteria help optimize patient triage to appropriate treatment regimens.

In 2001 Angela D. Levy et al, Gallbladder Carcinoma: Radiologic-Pathologic Correlation, Primary carcinoma of the gallbladder is an uncommon, aggressive malignancy that affects women more frequently than men. Older age groups are most often affected, and coexisting gallstones are present in the vast majority of cases. The symptoms at presentation are vague and are most often related to adjacent organ invasion.

Ultrasound reveals a mass replacing the normal gallbladder, diffuse or focal thickening of the gallbladder wall, or a polypoid mass within the gallbladder lumen. Adjacent organ invasion, most commonly involving the liver, is typically present at diagnosis, causing biliary obstruction. Periportal and peripancreatic lymphadenopathy, hematogenous metastases and peritoneal metastases are also seen.

Carcinomas that completely replace the gallbladder have irregular margins and heterogeneous echotexture at ultrasound. Heterogeneous echotexture reflects varying degrees of tumor necrosis. Echogenic foci and acoustic shadowing associated with the tumor may be related to coexisting gallstones, gallbladder wall calcification or tumoral calcification. Direct extension to the liver and biliary tree is a common associated finding with large, advanced carcinomas. In these cases, the tumor is inseparable from the adjacent liver.

Wall thickening is the most diagnostically challenging of the three patterns because it mimics the appearance of more common acute and chronic inflammatory conditions of the gallbladder. Subtle areas of wall thickening may reflect early carcinomas. However, they are difficult to detect, since they cause only mild elevation of the mucosa when viewed on ultrasound. Pronounced wall thickening (i.e., 1.0 cm or more) demonstrated by ultrasound, with associated mural irregularity or marked asymmetry should raise concerns for malignancy or complicated cholecystitis.

Knowledge of the varied appearances of gallbladder carcinoma at ultrasound is important so that the diagnosis can be considered preoperatively⁸⁷⁻⁸⁹.

In 2000, Manoj Pandey et al carcinoma of gallbladder: Role of sonography in diagnosing and staging, made an attempt to define the sonographic characteristics of gallbladder cancer. They retrospectively analyzed the sonographic findings in 203 cases of gallbladder cancer & confirmed by cytology or histopathology.

A mass in the gallbladder and gallbladder wall thickening (> 12 mm) were cardinal sonographic findings of carcinoma, their results have proved that ultrasound is highly accurate for detecting mass lesions, gallstones, liver infiltration, metastasis and ascites.

They concluded that sonography was found to be a good diagnostic tool for carcinoma of the gallbladder; however, its sensitivity was poor for staging nodal spread of the disease⁹⁰.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

**TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO FINAL
DIAGNOSIS**

FINAL DIAGNOSIS	N	%
ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS	25	12.4
ADENOMYOMATOSIS	1	0.5
CALCULOUS CHOLECYSTITIS	13	6.4
CALCULOUS CHOLECYSTITIS WITH ACUTE PANCREATITIS	1	0.5
CHOLECYSTITIS WITH ADENOMYOMATOSIS	1	0.5
CHOLELITHIASIS	110	54.5
CHOLELITHIASIS AND CHRONIC PANCREATITIS	1	0.5
CHOLELITHIASIS WITH ADENOMYOMATOSIS	1	0.5
CHOLELITHIASIS WITH SLUDGE	16	7.9
CHRONIC CHOLECYSTITIS	3	1.5
GB MALIGNANCY	2	1
GB PERFORATION	1	0.5
GB POLYPS	20	10
GB SLUDGE	5	2.5
MEMBRANOUS CHOLECYSTITIS	1	0.5
PANCREATITIS WITH ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS	1	0.5
TOTAL	202	100

FIGURE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO AGE

FIGURE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO SEX

TABLE 2: INCIDENCE OF CHOLELITHIASIS WITH AGE AND SEX

Sl. no	Age	Male	Female	Total
1	20	2	0	2
2	21-30	10	15	25
3	31-40	11	13	24
4	41-50	13	10	23
5	51-60	13	5	18
6	>60	7	11	18
Total		56	54(49%)	110

In present study, cholelithiasis was found in 110 cases, there were 56 males and 54 females. The maximum incidence was in 2nd and 3rd decades

FIGURE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO SIZE OF CALCULUS

**FIGURE 7: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO AGE AND SEX
AMONG ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS CASES**

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO GB WALL THICKNESS

GB WALL THICKNESS IN MM	N	%
4-5	22	10.9
6-8	20	9.9
9-10	3	1.5
Total	202	100

TABLE 4: MURPHY'S SIGN AND PERICHOLECYSTIC FLUID AMONG ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS CASES

	Total	ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS	% out of total
MURPHY'S SIGN	36	19	52.8
PERICHOLECYSTIC FLUID	26	16	61.5

Murphy's sign and pericholecystic fluid were found to be reliable indicators in cases of acute cholecystitis.

**TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO AGE AND SEX
AMONG CHOLELITHIASIS WITH SLUDGE CASES**

Age (yrs)	Male		Female		Total		p value
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
20	0	0.0	1	9.1	1	6.3	0.581
21-30	0	0.0	3	27.3	3	18.8	
31-40	0	0.0	1	9.1	1	6.3	
41-50	3	60.0	2	18.2	5	31.3	
51-60	1	20.0	3	27.3	4	25.0	
>60	1	20.0	1	9.1	2	12.5	
Total	5	100.0	11	100.0	16	100.0	

16 cases of cholelithiasis were associated with sludge

**TABLE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO AGE AND SEX
AMONG GB POLYPS CASES**

Age (yrs)	Male		Female		Total		p value
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
20	2	14.3	0	0.0	2	10.0	0.416
21-30	5	35.7	1	16.7	6	30.0	
31-40	3	21.4	4	66.7	7	35.0	
41-50	2	14.3	1	16.7	3	15.0	
51-60	2	14.3	0	0.0	2	10.0	
>60	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	
Total	14	100.0	6	100.0	20	100.0	

TABLE 7: DISTRIBUTION OF CASES ACCORDING TO NO. OF POLYPS

NO. OF POLYPS	N	%
1	15	7.4
2	0	0
3	4	2
4	0	0
5	1	0.5
Total	202	100

INCIDENCE OF GALLSTONES IN OTHER CONDITIONS

Following conditions, each of 1 case showed evidence of gallstones which include, adenomyomatosis, acute pancreatitis with cholecystitis and chronic pancreatitis.

INCIDENCE OF OTHER GALLBLADDER DISEASES

Adenomyomatosis -3

Membranous cholecystitis – 1

FIGURE 8: COMPARISON OF PARAMETERS BETWEEN CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL DIAGNOSIS

IMAGES

Case 1

CHOLELITHIASIS

FIG 9

FIG 10

USG image showing well defined hyperechoic focus with posterior acoustic shadowing, corresponding CT shows hyperattenuating gall stone at the neck of gall bladder

Case 2

GALLBLADDER SLUDGE

FIG 11

USG image showing hyperechoic content at the dependent part of the body and internal echoes indicative of sludge

Case 3

ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS

FIG 12

USG image showing thickening of gall bladder wall with mural edema and mild pericholecystic fluid

Case 4

CALCULUS CHOLECYSTITIS

FIG 13

USG image showing gall bladder wall thickening with echogenic focus within lumen

Case 5

MULTIPLE GALLBLADDER POLYPS

FIG 14

USG image showing multiple well defined echogenic foci adherent to wall

Case 6

ADENOMYOMATOSIS

FIG 15

USG image showing well defined hyperechoic focus with comet tail artefact

Case 7

MEMBRANOUS CHOLECYSTITIS

FIG 16

USG image showing well detached membranes within lumen and asymmetrical wall thickness

Case 8

CARCINOMA GALLBLADDER WITH HEPATIC INVASION

FIG 17FIG 18

USG image showing ill defined heteroechoic irregular mass lesion in gall bladder fossa completely obscuring gall bladder, corresponding CT shows heterogeneously hypodense lesion in the GB fossa with hepatic invasion

Case 9

GALLBLADDER MALIGNANCY

FIG 19FIG 20

USG image showing ill defined mass lesion nearly obscuring the lumen of gall bladder, corresponding CT shows heterogeneously hypodense lesion in the gall bladder

DISCUSSION

Gallbladder diseases are very common entities with diverse features of presentation at clinical, radiological settings, with variable morbidity and mortality with altered biliary function.

In our study, majority of them involve gallstones (54.5%), followed by inflammatory conditions and neoplasms.

Among inflammatory conditions, acute cholecystitis was common.

Others include membranous cholecystitis, polyps, adenomyomatosis and carcinoma.

Benign neoplasms are very rare, compared to malignant ones but are uncommon to inflammatory conditions.

Gallbladder diseases were seen in all age groups, with peak incidence at second and fifth decades.

Incidence of gallbladder diseases with age and sex

In our study there were 107 males and 95 females, and maximum incidence was seen in 2nd and 5th decades.

Clare Bayram et al. Gallbladder disease; has described that prevalence of GBD increases with age, and is more common in women than men⁹¹.

Both the studies showed similar age distribution however, there was male predominance noted in our study. This variation may be due to changing life style and limited period of study.

Incidence of gallstones with age and sex

In present study, cholelithiasis was found in 110 cases, there were 56 males and 54 females. The maximum incidence was in 2nd and 3rd decades.

Hardeep Singh Gill et al. epidemiology of gallstone disease; in a study of 50 cases, stated Gallstones occurred in relatively younger patients, fifty percent of whom were between 11-40 years while 24% were between 41-50 years and 4% were between 11-20 years, prevalence increased with age in both sexes reaching a maximum in the third decade in men and fourth decade in women⁹².

Incidence of gallstones in our study was 54% with detection accuracy of 100%.

Significance of size of gallstones

In our study, among 110 cases of cholelithiasis, 58 cases (28.7%) were between 6-10 mm, 29 cases were 11-15 mm and 20 cases in range of 16-20 mm.

In a similar study done by Sultan Alshoabi⁹³ on the gallstones and their characteristics like site, size, prevalence by ultrasonography, observed 184 patients with gallstones, 11-20 mm in 54 cases (29.51%), followed by less than 5mm in 38 cases (20.77%), 20-30 mm in 24 cases (13.11%) and so on.

Results were similar in both the studies.

Association of cholelithiasis with sludge:

In our study, 16 cases of cholelithiasis were associated with sludge of which 11 were females and 5 were males, most common in the 4th decade and in females.

In a similar study by Sauerland S. stated, children under the age of 16 years rarely develop gallstones. In adults, prevalence steadily increases; female gender is an important risk factor for biliary lithiasis⁹⁴.

Incidence of acute cholecystitis with age and sex:

Among 25 cases, 13 were males and 12 females, after 2nd decade incidence increased with age.

In a similar study done by, Eskelinen M et al. Acute cholecystitis cases account for 3%–10% of all patients with abdominal pain among 1333 patients⁹⁵.

Telfer S et al. The percentage of acute cholecystitis cases in patients under 50 years old with abdominal pain (n = 6317) was low, at 6.3%, whereas that in patients aged 50 years and over (n = 2406) was high, at 20.9%⁹⁶.

Both the studies showed similar results of increased prevalence with age group.

GB wall thickness in acute cholecystitis:

In our study, wall thickness of more than 3 mm is taken as cut-off value for acute cholecystitis, 22 cases were between 4-5 mm, 20 cases in range of 6-8 mm, 3 cases of 9-10 mm.

In a similar study, Deitch and Engel J M. Thickening of the gallbladder wall is the most reliable criterion with reported specificity of 90% using 3.0 mm and 98.5% at a 3.5 mm wall thickness, whereas sensitivity was 100% at 3.0 mm but only 80% at 3.5 mm, they recommended acceptance of gallbladder wall thickness of 3.5 mm or

greater as definitive evidence of acute cholecystitis, whereas 3.0 mm is suggestive but not conclusive evidence⁹⁷.

Murphy's sign and pericholecystic fluid in acute cholecystitis:

In acute cholecystitis along with wall thickness of >3mm, sonographic Murphy's sign and pericholecystic fluid were found to be more reliable indicators.

In a similar study done by Vriesman AC et al, In 2007, Accuracy in diagnosing acute cholecystitis increased when using a combination of findings including cholelithiasis, gallbladder wall thickening and a positive sonographic Murphy's sign³⁶.

Incidence of calculus cholecystitis with age and sex:

In our study, there were 13 cases with 10 males and 3 females, 6 patients were seen between 41-60 yrs in males and all 3 females are in the age group of 21-30 yrs.

In a similar study done by R. Jai Vinod Kumar et al, studied among 50 cases, 33 were females and 17 were males and maximum incidence was seen in 3rd and 4th decades⁹⁸.

In contrast to the above study male predominance was seen in our study and increased incidence was also seen in 5th decade.

Incidence of GB polyps with age and sex

In present study, there were 20 cases of gallbladder polyps with 14 males and 6 females, increased age of incidence in 21 – 40 yrs.

In a similar study W Kratzer et al. studied among 1027 patients, 128 cases were GB polyps and sex incidence was fairly equal of about 6.1 % each, average age of presentation was 42 yrs⁹⁹.

Significance of size of GB polyps

In our study among 20 cases of GB polyps, 9 cases were between 3-4 mm, 3 cases each in 1-2 mm and 5-6 mm, remaining 5 cases were of 10 mm or greater.

Polyps of more than 10 mm were considered to be with increased risk of malignancy in older age group (>60 yrs) and were followed up with subsequent scans for increase in size.

In a similar study by Michael T. Corwin et al. studied on 346 patients with mean age 52 yrs (20–93 years) and found that risk of malignancy is more in polyps of 1 cm or more diameter, single polyp, sessile polyps, polyps with adjoining increased wall thickness and also with increasing age. When two or more polyps were recognized, and increase in size of 0.2 cm or more on follow-up study, was of significance. They were distinguished as stable, resolved, increased/reduced in size on the basis of the highest length measurement⁶¹.

Comparison between clinical and radiological diagnosis in cholelithiasis, acute cholecystitis, GB malignancy

In our study, cholelithiasis was detected without fail on ultrasound in 54% of cases which was far superior to clinical suspicion which was only 11.4 %, acute cholecystitis was detected both clinically and radiologically with equal rates of detection (12.4 %), and among 2 cases of malignancy, intraluminal mass replacing the gallbladder with intrahepatic biliary dilatation, adjacent hepatic invasion seen in one

case on both ultrasound and CT. In second case clinically it was suspected as hepatoma.

In 2007, Randi G et al, Mass Occupying or replacing the Gallbladder lumen, was seen in 40–65% of patients with gallbladder carcinoma at initial detection. On ultrasound the presence of a large gallbladder mass that replaces the lumen, directly invading the surrounding liver parenchyma is highly suggestive of gallbladder carcinoma.

In comparison, ultrasound reliably recognized both the malignant cases⁸⁵.

In 3 cases of focal adenomyomatosis, comet tail reverberation artefact was seen and is diagnostic feature.

In 2006 Boscak AR et al, Echogenic intramural foci from which emanate V-shaped comet tail reverberation artefacts representing the unique acoustic signature of cholesterol crystals within the lumen of Rokitansky-Aschoff sinuses, are highly specific for adenomyomatosis⁶³.

CONCLUSION

Gallbladder diseases are very common and it is appropriate to accentuate that, understanding of these conditions is essential. In present study of 202 patients, an attempt was made to correlate clinical & ultrasound features of gallbladder diseases and to ascertain the sensitivity of ultrasound in evaluation of gallbladder diseases.

The ultrasound diagnosis in gallbladder diseases had favourable & impressive results against clinical diagnosis.

Ultrasound could detect gallstones and acute cholecystitis unfailingly; other conditions such as calculous cholecystitis, cholelithiasis with sludge, adenomyomatosis, polyps, membranous cholecystitis, carcinoma were also diagnosed.

Only in cases of chronic cholecystitis ultrasound had limited diagnostic value since wall thickness was not appreciable in all the cases and hence it was tricky to recognize without prior clinical history.

In case of malignancy, ultrasound was inferior to CT in staging and also in detecting lymph nodes.

The use of ultrasound is rapid taking only few minutes, non-invasive, no ionizing radiation, easy to perform and interpret, cost effective with good repeatability and reliability, the features which help to score over other imaging modalities in emergency situations.

SUMMARY

Gallbladder diseases include gamut of conditions, and are seen almost everyday in radiology practice, early detection of which helps in bringing down the morbidity and mortality associated with them.

Patients with gallbladder diseases usually presents with pain in the right hypochondriac region. Certain conditions like carcinoma gallbladder present with vague manifestations, cases of gallbladder polyps are asymptomatic.

In such conditions, the inclusion of ultrasound abdomen in routine investigation protocol will help in early diagnosis and initiation of therapy.

Ultrasound has the highest sensitivity and specificity for evaluating patients with suspected biliary pathologies.

Abdominal ultrasound is the first imaging technique employed for patients presenting with biliary-type symptoms as it is more accurate than CT for diagnosing acute biliary diseases.

The overall good sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosis of gallbladder diseases has led to the proposition that ultrasound is the diagnostic technique of choice in evaluation of gallbladder diseases.

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ANNEXURES

ANNEXURE I

B.L.D.E. UNIVERSITY'S
SHRI.B.M.PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, BIJAPUR – 586103
INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL COMMITTEE

No/56/2015
20/11/15

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this college met on 17-11-2015 at 03 pm
scrutinize the Synopsis of Postgraduate Students of this college from Ethical
Clearance point of view. After scrutiny the following original/corrected and
revised version synopsis of the Thesis has accorded Ethical Clearance.

Title "Ultrasound Study of Gall bladder diseases"

— x — x — x — x —
— x — x — x — x —

Name of P.G. Student : Dr. Holebasu
Dept of Radiology

Name of Guide/Co-investigator : Dr. B.R. Dhamangaonkar
professor

DR. TEJASWINI VALLABHA
CHAIRMAN

CHAIRMAN

Following documents were placed before E.C. for Scrutinizing Institutional Ethical Committee
1) Copy of Synopsis/Research Project
2) Copy of informed consent form.
3) Any other relevant documents.

Institutional Ethical Committee
BLDEU's Shri B.M. Patil
Medical College, BIJAPUR-586103.

ANNEXURE II

CASE PROFORMA

Name: Age: Sex: MRD No:

Chief complaints:

History of present illness:

1. Pain abdomen
2. Vomiting
3. Fever

PAST HISTORY:

FAMILY HISTORY:

PERSONAL HISTORY:

CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS:

ANNEXURE – III

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

B.L.D.E.U.'s SHRI B.M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND
RESEARCH CENTRE, BIJAPUR – 586103, KARNATAKA

TITLE OF THE PROJECT : ULTRASOUND STUDY
OF GALLBLADDER DISEASES

PRINCIPAL INVESTEGATOR : DR.HOLEBASU

DEPARTMENT OF RADIOLOGY

Email:holebasu@yahoo.co.in

PG GUIDE : DR.B.R.DHAMANGAONKAR_{MDRD}
PROFESSOR
DEPT. OF RADIOLOGY
BLDE UNIVERSITY'S,
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL
COLLEGE
VIJAYAPURA.

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed that this is being done to describe the role of ultrasound in evaluation of gallbladder diseases.

I have been explained about the reason for doing this study and selecting me/my ward as a subject for this study. I have also been given free choice for either being included or not in the study.

PROCEDURE:

I/my ward have been explained that, I/my ward will be subjected to ultrasound scan of abdomen to describe various diseases regarding the gallbladder.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS:

I/my ward understand that necessary measures will be taken to reduce these complications as and when they arise.

BENEFITS:

I/my ward understand that my participation in this study will describe the role of ultrasound in the study of gallbladder diseases.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I/my ward understand that medical information produced by this study will become a part of this Hospital records and will be subjected to the confidentiality and privacy regulation of this hospital. Information of a sensitive, personal nature will not be a part of the medical records, but will be stored in the investigators research file

and identified only by a code number. The code key connecting name to numbers will be kept in a separate secure location.

If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purpose, no names will be used and other identifiers such as photographs and audio or video tapes will be used only with my special written permission. I understand that I may see the photograph and videotapes and hear audiotapes before giving this permission.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time. **Dr.Holebasu** is available to answer my questions or concerns. I/my ward understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of this study, which might influence my continued participation.

If during this study, or later, I wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social worker of the hospital is available to talk with me. And that a copy of this consent form will be given to me for careful reading.

REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I/my ward understand that my participation is voluntary and I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital.

I/my ward also understand that Dr.Holebasuwill terminate my participation in this study at any time after he has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or therapist, if this is appropriate.

INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me/my ward, resulting directly to my participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, then medical treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation will be provided.

I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study, I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of this research, the procedures required and the possible risks and benefits, to the best of my ability in patient's own language.

Date:

Dr. B.R.Dhamangaonkar

Dr. Holebasu

(Guide)

(Investigator)

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT:

I/my ward confirm that Dr.Holebasu has explained to me the purpose of this research, the study procedure that I will undergo and the possible discomforts and benefits that I may experience, in my own language.

I/my ward have been explained all the above in detail in my own language and I understand the same. Therefore I agree to give my consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

(Participant)

Date

(Witness to above signature)

Date

KEY TO MASTER CHART

ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS	-	AC
CHRONIC LIVER DISEASE	-	CLD
ACUTE GASTRITIS	-	AG
ACUTE PEPTIC DISEASE	-	APD
OBSTRUCTIVE JAUNDICE	-	OJ
PANCREATITIS	-	P
CHOLELITHIASIS	-	CL
CARCINOMA GB	-	CA GB
ALCHOLIC LIVER DISEASE	-	ALD
GALLBLADDER	-	GB
SLUDGE	-	SL
CALCULOUS CHOLECYSTITIS	-	CC

SL N O.	NAME	AGE/S EX	DATE	OPI P NO.	CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS	SONOGRAPHC MURPHY'S SIGN	SIZE OF CALCULUS IN MM	S L	GB WALL THICKNESS IN MM	PERICHOLECTIC FLUID	FOCAL WALL THICKENING WITH VASCULARITY ON COLOR DOPPLER	NO. AND SIZE OF POLYP IN MM	DETACHED MEMBRANES	ADENOMYOMATOSIS	PERFORATION	CT FINDINGS	FINAL DIAGNOSIS
1	DEEKSHA	6/F	2.11.2015	401523	AC	Y	A	A	5	P	A	A	A	A	A		AC
2	NIRMALA	12/F	2.11.2015	35713	HEPATITIS	N	A	P	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		GB SL
3	KALLAPPA	54/M	4.11.2015	404385	CLD	N	8	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL
4	LALITA	30/F	10.11.2015	412487	AG	N	14	P	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL WITH SL
5	GURABAI	52/F	10.11.2015	412506	APD	N	6	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL
6	SHAILA	22/F	12.11.2015	36723	AG	N	A	P	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		GB SL
7	HANAMANTAPPA	63/M	13.11.2015	414802	CLD	N	A	A	8	P	A	A	A	A	A		AC
8	DEEPA	21/F	16.11.2015	418338	AC	Y	7	A	6	P	A	A	A	A	A		CC
9	GOURAMMA	66/F	19.11.2015	422691	AG	N	18	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL
10	BASAVARAJ	63/M	24.11.2015	38043	APD	N	10	P	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL WITH SL
11	MEGHA	6/F	26.11.2015	38308	OJ	Y	A	A	5	P	A	A	A	A	A		AC
12	RAMAGOND	45/M	28.11.2015	434801	CL	N	17	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL
13	ZAMEER	50/M	1.12.2015	439173	P	N	A	A	5	A	A	A	A	A	A		AC
14	KASIMSAB	50/M	3.12.2015	441943	CLD	N	9	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL
15	GEETA	36/F	4.12.2015	39181	AG	N	15	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL
16	PRAKASH	60/M	4.12.2015	442065	APD	N	A	A	A	A	A	1 3	A	A	A		GB POLYP
17	SULOCHANA	40/F	8.12.2015	447109	AC	Y	A	A	6	P	A	A	A	A	A		AC
18	KEERTI	45/F	9.12.2015	449602	HEPATITIS	N	A	A	A	A	A	3 3	A	A	A		GB POLYPS
19	MEENAXI	42/F	16.12.2015	457573	P	N	A	A	5	P	A	A	A	A	A		AC
20	TUBSUM	65/F	17.12.2015	40610	PUO	N	12	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL
21	BAYAKKA	43/F	18.12.2015	460481	AC	Y	A	A	10	P	A	A	A	A	A		AC
22	SHIVAKUMAR	44/M	21.12.2015	465162	APD	N	16	P	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL WITH SL
23	SHANTABAI	69/F	22.12.2015	41175	PUO	N	9	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL
24	MANJULA	46/F	26.12.2015	469979	CL		14	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A		CL
25	MALLIKARJUN	32/M	5.1.2016	4837	AG	N	6	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	CL
26	GURU	28/M	8.1.2016	715	AG	N	7	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	CL
27	KRISHNAPPA	70/M	9.1.2016	861	AC	Y	A	A	6.6	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	AC
28	PARAGOND	55/M	10.1.2016	12105	AC	Y	9	A	4.8	P	A	A	A	A	A	A	CC
29	BHUVANESHWARI	45/F	12.1.2016	1106	HEPATITIS	Y	A	A	6	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	AC
30	MAHADEVI	52/F	19.1.2016	23439	APD	N	A	P	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	GB SL	GB SL
31	MALLAPPA	58/M	19.1.2016	1937	OJ	N	A	P	4	A	Y	A	A	A	A	AC	AC
32	SAHEBI	40/F	20.1.2016	25580	CL	N	30	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	CL
33	SAVITRI	30/F	21.1.2016	25541	AC	Y	9	A	7	P	A	A	A	A	A	A	CC

